

NOx reduction methods in burners and different types of Low NOx burners

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Abstract

In the last decade, due to the rapid increase of air pollution and the production of greenhouse gases caused by the combustion of hydrocarbon fuels, different countries have applied stricter laws to control the emission of greenhouse gases from industries and cars. In the process of combustion in heating devices, in addition to the formation of pollutants such as CO and CO₂, another pollutant gas is also formed, which is the product of the reaction of nitrogen and air oxygen at the flame temperature and is generally shown as NO_x. In burners, the higher the flame temperature, the higher the amount of NO_x. By managing the fuel and air combustion process, Low NO_x burners provide conditions to reduce their pollutant production. During this process, achieving stability and appropriate flame dimensions is a challenge that requires proper design. For this reason, in this article we will examine different applications of Low NO_x burners and methods of reducing NO_x in burners with different methods.

Keywords: Burner, Low NO_x, Combustion, Fuel